

Air quality and health effects of U.S. energy transitions

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Abstract

Transitioning the U.S. energy system has the potential to improve public health by reducing ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exposure. We develop an integrated modeling framework, coupling energy systems, air quality, and health effect models to evaluate cumulative and disparate PM_{2.5}-related health impacts associated with climate change mitigation, with explicit treatment of uncertainties that propagate along the modeling chain. We use this approach to assess the health effects that could have been induced by the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) and a more ambitious scenario to achieve net-zero emissions by midcentury. Largely driven by changes in the electricity and transportation sectors, avoided premature deaths in 2035 are similar in the IRA (6,850; CI: 6,040–7,660) and net-zero (8,350; CI: 7,350–9,330) scenarios. Cumulatively, the IRA scenario prevents 133,000 (CI: 117,000–149,000) premature deaths from 2022–2050, compared to 280,000 (CI: 247,000–313,000) in the net-zero scenario. This translates to cumulative monetized benefits of \$1.41 trillion (CI: \$0.14–3.71 trillion) in the IRA scenario, potentially exceeding federal tax credit net expenditures. Uncertainty in health benefits is influenced by the exposure–response function and, to a slightly lesser extent, the choice of air quality model. PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates decline over time for all racial/ethnic groups, but relative disparities persist. Sociodemographic dynamics, particularly population growth and aging, are the principal determinants of future PM_{2.5}-attributable health burdens, especially among Asian and Hispanic populations, whereas structural energy system changes influence the scale of associated health benefits of PM_{2.5} exposure reductions.

Significance Statement

Policies intended to reduce greenhouse gas emissions through a clean energy transition can also improve health by reducing air pollution emissions. We develop an integrated modeling framework that links energy systems, air quality, and health models while explicitly capturing uncertainties that propagate along the modeling chain. Applying this framework to the Inflation Reduction Act and a more ambitious net-zero pathway shows that decarbonization of the electricity

and transportation sectors produces comparable near-term health benefits, with larger cumulative benefits under deeper climate change mitigation. Racial/ethnic disparities in air pollution mortality persist given the influence of sociodemographic factors on future health burdens. The scale and distribution of health benefits is meaningfully shaped by cascading uncertainties.

Introduction

Exposure to ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) is the leading environmental risk factor for disease globally (1) and accounts for an estimated 100,000–200,000 premature deaths annually in the United States (2, 3). Despite overall decreases in PM_{2.5} emissions (4), exposure (5, 6), and mortality rates (7) over the past few decades, exposure disparities persist across socioeconomic and racial/ethnic groups (5, 8, 9). Policies intended to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions have the potential to produce substantial health benefits through concomitant reductions in air pollution (2, 10–18), though these measures will not necessarily reduce racial/ethnic exposure disparities (19–22).

Several studies have assessed the potential air quality and health effects of climate change mitigation either by constructing stylized scenarios in which specified GHG emissions reduction targets are achieved (20, 23, 24), assuming air pollutant emissions scale with carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (12, 19), or treating air pollutant emission removals as instantaneous (2, 16, 21). Other work has modeled specific policy instruments such as solar and wind power deployment (25, 26), clean energy standards (11, 27, 28), cap-and-trade programs (11, 29), carbon taxes (13, 28), and national renewable energy mandates (22).

In 2022, the U.S. government passed the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), which was designed to incentivize clean energy and carbon management, encourage electrification and energy efficiency measures, support domestic supply chains, and address labor and environmental justice concerns (30). A few studies have quantified the air quality and health effects potentially induced by the IRA, including analyses of the electric power sector (31, 32), multiple sectors (33, 34), and the combined effects of federal and state climate policies (35). Building on previous studies, we model multiple pollutants, sectors, and temporal scales and account for cascading uncertainties along the modeling chain – from technology selection and emissions to concentrations, population exposure, health effects, and monetized damages – that can meaningfully shape the magnitude and distribution of air pollution impacts.

Here, we develop and apply an integrated modeling framework that couples energy systems, air quality, and health effect models to evaluate cumulative and disparate PM_{2.5}-related health impacts associated with climate change mitigation policies and pathways in the United States. This approach accounts for uncertainty associated with the choice of air quality model, exposure–response functions, racial/ethnic stratification of mortality rates, and valuation of health effects. We also include a decomposition analysis to isolate the effects of population growth, population aging, mortality rate changes, and exposure changes on future PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality burdens across racial/ethnic groups. This work is strengthened by the use of newly derived baseline mortality rate projections stratified by race/ethnicity. Specifically, we evaluate the air quality impacts of emission changes of primary PM_{2.5} and gaseous precursors – sulfur dioxide (SO₂),

nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ammonia (NH₃), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) – across 15 source categories from 2022–2050 that could have been induced by the IRA and a more ambitious scenario to achieve net-zero GHG emissions by mid-century. We do not account for effects of the One Big Beautiful Bill Act (OBBBA) of 2025, which modifies several of the clean energy provisions in the IRA (36).

Results and Discussion

The subsequent sections are organized to mirror the integrated modeling framework (see Fig. S1 for a conceptual diagram of the framework). First, we summarize emission changes from energy system transitions. We then assess the resultant changes in PM_{2.5} concentrations, comparing the performance of air quality models. We next evaluate avoided premature mortality and monetized damages, characterizing uncertainty associated with the choice of air quality model, exposure–response function, and racial/ethnic stratification of baseline mortality rates. Finally, we decompose PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality to isolate the contribution of sociodemographic factors and exposure changes on future mortality burdens and assess racial/ethnic disparities in PM_{2.5}-related health impacts.

Emission Changes. Emission changes from energy system activity changes in select categories in the electricity, transportation, residential, commercial, and fossil fuel production sectors are simulated for the baseline, IRA, and net-zero scenarios. These sectors constitute 5.6% (primary PM_{2.5}), 58% (SO₂), 51% (NO_x), 3.6% (NH₃), and 10% (VOC) of total emissions (including biogenic and wildfire emissions) in the contiguous United States as reported in the 2017 NEI (37). Emissions of primary PM_{2.5} and gaseous precursors decline in the IRA and net-zero scenarios relative to the baseline (Fig. S2), largely driven by changes in the electricity and transportation sectors, although the nature of changes differs across scenarios. Driven almost exclusively by retirements of coal-fired power plants, SO₂ emissions decrease 72% from 2022 levels by 2035 in the IRA scenario and 93% in the net-zero scenario, representing the largest reduction of any pollutant. Primary PM_{2.5} emissions decline across all sectors, although in the transportation sector, increased tire and brake wear resulting from higher vehicle miles traveled largely offset reductions in exhaust emissions (Fig. S3). The IRA scenario induces greater NO_x emission reductions from transportation in 2035 than in the net-zero scenario, reflecting faster rates of electric and low-emission vehicle adoption under the IRA scenario in the near term. Oil and gas production remains the predominant source of VOC emission across all years and scenarios, while the contribution from transportation wanes in later years. In general, emission reductions are of similar magnitude in the IRA and net-zero scenarios until 2035, after which relatively higher reductions occur in the net-zero scenario.

Air Quality Impacts. We simulate PM_{2.5} concentration responses to emission changes induced by energy system activity changes using three reduced-complexity air quality models: the Air Pollution Social Cost Accounting (APSCA) model (38), the CO-Benefits Risk Assessment (COBRA) screening tool (39), and the InMAP Source-Receptor Matrix (ISRM) (40). We first evaluate air quality model performance by comparing modeled county-level 2022 baseline PM_{2.5} concentrations with satellite-derived PM_{2.5} observations (41) and U.S. EPA Air Quality System (AQS) monitoring data from 2017 (42). Baseline concentrations from COBRA strongly correlate with satellite-derived observations (Pearson correlation coefficient, $r = 0.70$) and AQS

observations ($r = 0.64$), outperforming APSCA ($r = 0.34$ and $r = 0.32$, respectively) and ISRM ($r = 0.44$ and $r = 0.37$, respectively). Moreover, large shares of the U.S. population reside in counties in which modeled exposure levels broadly agree (i.e. $\leq 25\%$ difference) with satellite-derived observations (APSCA, 48%; COBRA, 73%; ISRM, 54%). Additional model performance statistics can be found in Fig. S4.

We find that PM_{2.5} concentrations decline in future years in the IRA and net-zero scenarios relative to the baseline (Fig. 1; Fig. S5), with larger and more sustained reductions in the net-zero scenario. Across air quality models, population-weighted PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2035 in the contiguous United States average 0.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (model range: 0.13–0.22 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) below baseline in the IRA scenario and 0.21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (0.14–0.28 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) below baseline in the net-zero scenario. By 2050, this difference increases to 0.38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (0.30–0.50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) below baseline in the net-zero scenario, while this difference attenuates in the IRA scenario to 0.13 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (0.12–0.16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) below baseline. Consistently across years and scenarios, the largest and smallest concentration changes are reported by ISRM and COBRA, respectively. We assess inter-model differences in the spatial distribution of concentration changes using the Jensen–Shannon divergence (JSD) (43). Details on this approach are provided in SI Appendix, section S2, and quantitative results using the JSD are provided in SI Appendix, section S8. These results show that, although the three air quality models produce differing estimates of the magnitude of PM_{2.5} changes associated with identical emission changes, the spatial distribution of PM_{2.5} changes is similar across models.

Health and Economic Impacts and Uncertainty Analysis. We estimate avoided premature mortality and monetized damages resulting from PM_{2.5} exposure reductions. Mortality is estimated using the Global Exposure Mortality Model (GEMM) function (44) unless otherwise noted, and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) in mortality estimates reflect uncertainty in the hazard ratio function. Monetized damages are reported in 2022 U.S. dollars and assume no discounting in future years, and 95% CIs account for uncertainty in both the value of a statistical life and the hazard ratio function.

We find that the IRA scenario prevents 6,850 (CI: 6,040–7,660) premature deaths in 2035, 82% of the 8,350 (CI: 7,350–9,330) premature deaths prevented in the net-zero scenario in the same year (Fig. 2), assuming model-averaged concentration changes. This translates to \$73 billion (CI: \$7.1–193 billion) in monetized benefits in 2035 in the IRA scenario and \$88 billion (CI: \$8.6–235 billion) in the net-zero scenario. In 2035, emission reductions in the transportation sector in the IRA scenario generate nearly the same health benefit, 3,370 (CI: 2,970–3,770) avoided premature deaths, as reductions from reduced coal electricity generation in the net-zero scenario, which prevent 3,670 (CI: 3,230–4,100) premature deaths. Policies to incentivize adoption of certain clean technologies, such as the electric vehicle tax credit provisions in the IRA, have the potential to generate similar benefits as strategies that prioritize coal retirement, which are commonly emphasized in stylized least-cost optimization pathways to achieve net-zero emissions. This further highlights the role of policy sequencing, whereby shifts in the order and timing of sectoral emission reduction strategies need not diminish resultant health benefits. By 2050, avoided premature deaths in the net-zero scenario increase to 17,090 (CI: 15,040–19,100) while the IRA scenario results in 5,790 (CI: 5,100–6,470) avoided premature deaths, equivalent to avoided damages of \$181 billion (CI: \$18–472 billion) and \$61 billion (CI: \$6.0–162 billion), respectively.

Cumulatively, the IRA scenario prevents 133,000 (CI: 117,000–149,000) premature deaths from 2022–2050, compared to 280,000 (CI: 247,000–313,000) avoided premature deaths projected in the net-zero scenario, meaning that the IRA could have provided nearly half (47%) the PM_{2.5}-related health benefits of a more ambitious net-zero pathway. Equivalently, cumulative monetized benefits are \$1.41 trillion (CI: \$0.14–3.71 trillion) in the IRA scenario and \$2.97 trillion (CI: \$0.29–7.82 trillion) in the net-zero scenario. The cumulative PM_{2.5}-related health benefits of the climate and energy provisions of the IRA could have slightly exceeded their costs; we estimate that cumulative federal tax credit net expenditures from 2022–2050 could have been \$1.07 trillion (45). See SI Appendix, section S9, for monetized benefit totals using alternative discount rates and a comparison to federal budget outlays projections.

Over the presumed effective life of the law (2022–2035), the IRA could have prevented 33,400 (CI: 29,500–37,400) premature deaths. Notably, the air quality and health benefits of the IRA could have persisted after the expiration of its provisions, with 99,500 (CI: 87,600–111,000) premature deaths avoided from 2036–2050, nearly three times the benefits accrued when provisions would have been in effect. This finding highlights the potential durability of health benefits associated with deep structural changes in the energy system – the electrification of transport and the phasedown of fossil fuel power plants – that are not readily reversed after infrastructure is deployed or retired.

The sectoral distribution of benefits differs across scenarios. In the IRA scenario, emission reductions from vehicle sectors account for nearly two-thirds (64%; model range: 61–70%) of total benefits from 2022–2050, cumulatively preventing 84,300 (CI: 74,200–94,100) premature deaths. About half (51%; range: 49–54%) of cumulative benefits in the IRA scenario are attributable to emission reductions in just two sectors: heavy-duty vehicles (27%; range: 24–33%) and light-duty trucks (24%; range: 22–25%). The next largest sources of cumulative benefits in the IRA scenario are coal electricity generation (15%; range: 12–18%), residential natural gas (11%; range: 8.9–14%), buses (7.0%; range: 5.6–9.1%), and passenger cars (6.2%; range: 5.0–6.8%). By contrast, in the net-zero scenario, coal electricity generation provides more than one-third (38%; range: 30–42%) of total benefits from 2022–2050, followed by heavy-duty vehicles (14%; range: 12–18%), residential natural gas (10%; range: 8.8–12%), light-duty trucks (8.8%; range: 8.3–8.9%), oil and gas production (6.3%; range: 3.1–8.9%), and natural gas electricity generation (5.7%; range: 5.0–6.9%). The sectoral distribution of benefits is broadly consistent across models in a given year and is largely insensitive to the choice of exposure–response function (Fig. S6).

We characterize uncertainty associated with the choice of air quality model, exposure–response function, and racial/ethnic stratification of baseline mortality rates (Fig. 3; Fig. S7). Accounting for all three choices, avoided premature mortality totals vary by a factor of 3.2–4.4 across scenarios in select years (2035 and 2050); factors indicate the ratio of avoided premature mortality reported by the combination of modeling choices that produce the largest and smallest totals in a given year and scenario. The combined effects of these modeling choices are more pronounced in the net-zero scenario (factor of 4.4 in 2035; 3.8 in 2050) than the IRA scenario (3.8; 3.2) and more pronounced in 2035 than 2050 within a given scenario (Fig. 3; Fig. S7). The choice of exposure–response function has the greatest effect, with avoided premature mortality totals differing by a factor of 2.3 across scenarios and models in select years. The choice of air quality model results in a factor of 1.4–2.0 difference in avoided premature mortality totals across years and scenarios.

Stratifying baseline mortality rates by race/ethnicity has a relatively minor effect (i.e. $\leq 4\%$ difference) when considering the overall population, although it meaningfully influences the distribution of avoided premature mortality totals by racial/ethnic group (details in SI Appendix, section S10). These results suggest that the choice of exposure–response function and air quality model are both important considerations for health-relevant air quality benefits assessment.

Decomposition Analysis. We decompose PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality, isolating the contribution of three sociodemographic factors (population growth, population aging, mortality rate changes) and exposure changes. The decomposition analysis approach is detailed in SI Appendix, section S5. Ambient PM_{2.5} exposure led to 185,000 (CI: 162,000–207,000) premature deaths in the contiguous United States in 2022 (Fig. S8), assuming model-averaged concentrations. In the baseline scenario, PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality increases, reaching 209,000 (CI: 184,000–235,000; +13%) in 2035 and 213,000 (CI: 187,000–238,000; +15%) in 2050. Over time, increasing burdens from population growth and aging more than offset decreases from mortality rate and exposure changes (Fig. 4). Though the net effect of the four factors is comparable over time, the contribution of each factor approximately doubles from 2035 to 2050: population growth (+14% in 2035; +28% in 2050), population aging (+22%; +35%), mortality rate changes (–19%; –39%), and exposure changes (–4.9%; –9.7%). Relative to the baseline scenario, larger exposure reductions in the IRA and net-zero scenarios result in smaller net increases in future health burdens. These changes indicate that continued growth and aging of the U.S. population will lead to increasing PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality burdens that are largely, but not entirely, offset by declining mortality rates and PM_{2.5} exposures, even in ambitious emission reduction scenarios.

Sociodemographic and exposure changes lead to net increases in PM_{2.5}-attributable deaths in future years for most racial/ethnic groups (Fig. 4). The effects of population growth and aging are most pronounced for Asian and Hispanic populations. By 2050, PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality in the baseline scenario approximately triples among Asian Americans (+185%) and Hispanic Americans (+206%) because of population growth and aging. Accounting for all four factors, health burdens more than double by 2050 for Asian Americans (+104%) and Hispanic Americans (+124%). The net effect of sociodemographic and exposure changes is less pronounced for Black Americans and White Americans. Health burdens among Native populations decrease by approximately 15% in both 2035 and 2050, reflecting slow population growth and population aging that do not offset reductions attributable to declining mortality rates and PM_{2.5} exposure. (Results showing the changing share of avoided PM_{2.5} mortality benefits by racial/ethnic group in future years in the IRA and net-zero scenarios are provided in SI Appendix, section S11.) These results indicate that sociodemographic changes, particularly among Asian and Hispanic populations, will increasingly shape future PM_{2.5} health burdens and the racial/ethnic distribution of benefits of emission reductions.

Racial/Ethnic Disparity Impacts. We characterize racial/ethnic disparities in health impacts using multiple metrics of relative and absolute difference within and between population groups; methods are detailed in SI Appendix, section S6. To compare health effects across racial/ethnic groups, we evaluate age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates. We find that mortality rates decline in the future in the overall population (Fig. S9) and for all racial/ethnic groups (Fig. 5) across all scenarios. There are larger absolute reductions in mortality rates in the IRA and net-zero scenarios than the baseline. Across all years and scenarios, PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates

remain highest for Black and lowest for Asian populations (Fig. 5). Absolute disparities in mortality rates between racial/ethnic groups narrow over time, as mortality rates decline most sharply for Black populations (Fig. S10). Relative disparities, measured as percent differences in mortality rates, persist across years and scenarios, though they narrow slightly for some racial/ethnic groups (Fig. S10). The choice of exposure-response function influences mortality rates (Figs. S11, S12); using another function results in smaller absolute disparities but similar relative disparities (Fig. S13). These findings indicate that PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates will decline for all racial/ethnic groups as PM_{2.5} concentrations decrease over time but that relative disparities in mortality rates between racial/ethnic groups will persist even as absolute disparities narrow. Larger PM_{2.5} concentration decreases in the IRA and net-zero scenarios lead to slightly steeper mortality rate declines for all racial/ethnic groups, but these scenarios do not meaningfully narrow racial/ethnic mortality rate disparities relative to the baseline.

We also assess inequality in the distribution of avoided PM_{2.5}-related deaths by race/ethnicity using the Gini coefficient (G), a standard measure of inequality ranging from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (perfect inequality). Gini coefficients for all years, scenarios, models, and racial/ethnic groups are shown in Fig. S14, and further results are provided in SI Appendix, section S12. Compared to the overall population ($G = 0.34$), benefits in the IRA scenario in 2035 are similar for Asian ($G = 0.35$), Hispanic ($G = 0.31$) and Native ($G = 0.32$) populations, and less unequal for Black ($G = 0.26$) and White ($G = 0.26$) populations (Fig. S14), assuming model-averaged concentration changes. For all racial/ethnic groups, benefit distributions are similarly unequal in 2035 in the IRA and net-zero scenarios ($\Delta G \leq 0.02$) (Fig. S14). By 2050, benefits are more unequally distributed in the IRA scenario than the net-zero scenario for all racial/ethnic groups, though inequality remains lowest among White Americans and highest among Asian Americans. These findings show that the IRA could have provided similarly equal benefit distributions as a more ambitious net-zero pathway in the near term, but that both scenarios produce more widespread benefit for White populations than non-White populations.

Conclusion

This study indicates that a clean energy transition in the United States has the potential to generate substantial air quality and public health benefits. This finding is robust to several sources of uncertainty, although the magnitude of benefits is influenced by the model functional form, including the choice of air quality model and exposure–response function and, to a lesser extent, the racial/ethnic stratification of mortality rates. This study further highlights the contrast between a stylized scenario to achieve net-zero emissions by midcentury and a real-world transition scenario that explicitly represents the suite of policies enacted under the IRA. In both scenarios, PM_{2.5} exposure reductions largely result from declines in electric power and transportation emissions, although the pace and nature of reductions differ. The scale of PM_{2.5}-related health benefits is comparable between the IRA and net-zero scenarios in the near term, but differences in the scale of benefits increase over time as sociodemographic factors, particularly population growth and aging, increasingly offset reductions in PM_{2.5} exposure and baseline mortality rates. PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates decline over time for all racial/ethnic groups as a result of reduced PM_{2.5} exposure, but relative disparities in PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates persist in all scenarios. These findings indicate that sociodemographic dynamics are the principal determinants

of future PM_{2.5}-attributable health burdens, whereas structural changes in the energy system influence the scale of health benefits of PM_{2.5} exposure reductions.

These results have implications for climate, energy, and public health policy processes, including agenda-setting, design, and evaluation. The health benefits of climate change mitigation are often framed as ancillary co-benefits, but we show these benefits to be substantial. In addition, generating equitable long-term health benefits may require complementary policies targeting the transportation, building, and industrial sectors to explicitly address persistent disparities in air pollution exposure and mortality rates (7, 20). The integration of sociodemographic projections into policy design and evaluation is also important given their dominant role in shaping future air quality health burdens.

This work advances an integrated framework that couples modeling of energy systems, emissions, air quality, and human health, with explicit treatment of uncertainty across the modeling chain. Moreover, we introduce decomposition and racial/ethnic inequality analyses that enable quantification of how sociodemographic and technological drivers jointly determine future health outcomes. Our results also motivate several directions for future research. First, additional uncertainties not captured in this study arise from energy systems modeling, particularly in relation to technology adoption, diffusion rates, and spatial downscaling (46, 47). These assumptions can influence both the magnitude and distribution of air quality effects. Second, studies have shown that fine-scale dynamics of atmospheric processes have implications for the distribution of health effects (48, 49). While we employ three reduced-complexity air quality models, they mask some atmospheric process dynamics as a result of common simplifying assumptions, including the use of annual average concentrations, limited representation of future meteorology, and omission of ozone chemistry (50). Finally, while we explicitly model an enacted suite of policies, there are policy dynamics such as policy durability, sequencing (51), adaptability, and implementation uncertainty (52, 53) that we did not account for. This modeling framework can be applied to capture those dynamics and to provide insight into the design of policies in other national and subnational contexts. Moreover, cross-sector interactions between the electricity, transportation, building, industrial, and agricultural sectors can be further explored, as well as the influence of other PM_{2.5} sources (e.g. wildfires).

Materials and Methods

Policy and Planning Scenarios. We model the following three policy and planning scenarios: 1) baseline scenario that reflects policies enacted as of January 2021; 2) IRA scenario that includes mid-range assumptions about the effectiveness of provisions of the IRA (30) and Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act (IIJA) (54) and potential constraints on technology adoption rates; and 3) net-zero scenario in which economy-wide greenhouse gas emissions reach 51% below 2005 levels by 2030 and net zero by 2050. The IRA scenario excludes 2021 EPA greenhouse gas emission standards for passenger cars and light-duty trucks (55), 2022 air pollution emission standards for heavy-duty vehicles and engines (56), and provisions of the 2025 OBBBA that eliminate or expedite the phaseout of several provisions of the IRA (36), including electric vehicle tax credits and production tax credits for solar and wind power projects.

Activity Modeling. The energy system scenarios analyzed in this study are taken from Jenkins et al. (33), who through the Rapid Energy Policy Evaluation and Analysis Toolkit (REPEAT) project provide evaluations of federal energy and climate policies. Energy system modeling is conducted using EnergyPATHWAYS and the Regional Investment and Operations (RIO) model (57). EnergyPATHWAYS is a bottom-up stock-rollover accounting model that determines economy-wide electricity and fuel demand under large-scale energy system transformations. RIO is a linear programming capacity expansion model that finds the least-cost investments in energy supply needed to meet time-varying electricity and fuel demand specified by EnergyPATHWAYS. The baseline, IRA, and net-zero scenarios correspond to the “Frozen Policies,” “Current Policies (mid-range),” and “Net-Zero Pathway” scenarios, respectively, from Jenkins et al. (33). Details on the activity modeling downscaling approach are provided in SI Appendix, section S1.

Most demand-side technology adoption assumptions in the baseline scenario are based on the Annual Energy Outlook 2022 from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (58). The net-zero scenario is similar to the least-cost net-zero scenario described by Haley et al. (59). For a detailed description of the IRA and IIRA provisions that are modeled in the IRA scenario, see Jenkins et al. (60). Modeled IRA provisions include production tax credits for electricity produced from solar, wind, and geothermal facilities; investment tax credits for energy storage facilities; 45Q tax credits for carbon capture use and storage projects; tax credits and deductions for energy efficiency improvements in residential and commercial buildings, which cover electric and geothermal heat pumps, heat pump water heaters, and building components such as doors, windows, lighting, and HVAC systems; and tax credits for plug-in hybrid and electric vehicles.

Air Pollution Emissions. We model changes in county-level emissions of primary PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO_x, NH₃, and VOCs for 15 source categories that largely correspond to U.S. EPA Emissions Inventory System (EIS) sectors. We only model changes in emissions from source categories for which a direct effect from the IRA and net-zero scenarios is anticipated. For categories including non-road mobile, dust, fire, biogenic, and other sources, we hold emissions constant at 2017 levels in all years and scenarios, allowing the direct effects of the policies to be isolated. This analysis relies on emissions data from the 2017 Emissions Modeling Platform (61), which are based on data from the 2017 National Emissions Inventory (NEI) (37). We use these data for two main purposes: to serve as emission totals for all non-modeled sectors, and to impute additional data for modeled emissions sectors that are needed to support air quality modeling (details in SI Appendix, section S1).

Air Quality Modeling. We use three reduced-complexity air quality models to determine PM_{2.5} exposure: the Air Pollution Social Cost Accounting (APSCA) model (38) as parameterized by Ran and Tessum (62), the CO-Benefits Risk Assessment (COBRA) screening tool (version 4.7) (39), and the InMAP Source-Receptor Matrix (ISRM) (40). We harmonize model outputs by spatially attributing gridded PM_{2.5} concentration data from APSCA and ISRM to the county level using an area-weighting approach. The strengths and limitations of these and other reduced-complexity air quality models have been discussed in previous studies (14, 16, 21, 25, 26, 50, 63–65). In general, reduced-complexity models are more suitable for determining relative air quality differences across energy scenarios than absolute differences (46). Further detail on these models is provided in SI Appendix, section S2.

Satellite-derived PM_{2.5} data, which are used in model evaluation, are taken from the North American Regional Estimates with Composition (V5.NA.04.02) dataset (41), which combines satellite retrievals of aerosol optical depth with GEOS-Chem chemical transport modeling and ground-based monitor data to produce hybrid surface-level PM_{2.5} concentration estimates (41, 66). Satellite-derived data are reported at a resolution of 0.01° × 0.01°. We derive county-level exposure estimates by treating satellite-derived data as points and averaging all points within a county. Model outputs are also evaluated against ground-based regulatory monitor data from EPA's Air Quality System (AQS) (42). Modeled concentrations are compared to satellite-derived and monitoring observations from 2017 and not 2022 since non-modeled sectors in our emissions dataset are from the 2017 NEI.

Health Impact Modeling and Economic Valuation. To conduct health impact modeling, we recreate data and functions in Python (version 3.8.5) from version 1.5.8 of the Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program–Community Edition (BenMAP–CE) (67, 68). We use county-level population projections at one-year intervals from 2000 to 2050 in five-year age groups based on the 2010 U.S. Census (69), which are also taken from BenMAP–CE. While the air quality models used in this study can report health effects, we conduct all health impact modeling outside the models to ensure consistent data and assumptions.

We use a process similar to BenMAP–CE (70) to derive baseline all-cause and non-accidental mortality rates for each of the five racial/ethnic groups for which BenMAP–CE provides population data (i.e. White, Black, Hispanic, Asian, Native) in five-year age groups and five-year intervals from 2020 to 2050; these mortality rate data improve upon race/ethnicity-specific mortality rates in BenMAP–CE that include only two racial/ethnic groups (i.e. White and non-White), ten-year age groups, a single time period (i.e. 2007–2016 average), and only all-cause mortality. Baseline 2020 mortality rates are derived based on average 2018–2022 mortality count data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) WONDER database (71). These data are combined with population data, averaged over the same years, to calculate baseline county-, age-, and race/ethnicity-specific rates for all-cause and non-accidental mortality. We derive future-year mortality rates using data from the U.S. Census Bureau (72), which provides nationwide age- and race/ethnicity-specific all-cause mortality rate projections in five-year intervals from 2015 to 2060. Details on the methods used to derived new mortality rates are provided in SI Appendix, section S3, and an evaluation of new rates and default BenMAP–CE rates are provided in SI Appendix, section S7.

We use the Global Exposure Mortality Model (GEMM) function (44) as the primary exposure–response function in the main text. The GEMM function determines non-accidental mortality from PM_{2.5} among persons aged ≥25 based on 41 cohort studies from 16 countries. The function is near-linear at high concentrations (i.e. ≥20 µg/m³), supralinear at low concentrations, and applies a counterfactual threshold of 2.4 µg/m³. As sensitivities, we also estimate mortality burdens using exposure–response functions from the American Cancer Society Cancer Prevention Study II study (73), a study using National Health Interview Surveys data (74), and the Harvard Six Cities Study (75). Further details on exposure–response functions are provided in SI Appendix, section S3, and results using other functions are provided in the uncertainty analysis in the main text. Unless otherwise noted, mortality counts referenced in the main text use population data and race/ethnicity-stratified mortality rate data for the year nearest the analysis year. Methods for

economic valuation are provided in SI Appendix, section S4. Methods for the decomposition and racial/ethnic inequality analyses are provided in the SI Appendix, sections S5 and S6, respectively.

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Figures

Figure 1. County-level PM_{2.5} concentration changes relative to the same-year baseline by year, scenario, and model. Values at the bottom left of panels show differences in the population-weighted concentration (Δ PWC) from the baseline scenario. APSCA and ISRM data have been area-weighted to counties from their original grid definitions.

Figure 2. Avoided PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths by year, scenario, model, and sector. Shaded regions in the top panels indicate 95% confidence intervals that reflect uncertainty in the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (44). Labeled years are modeled; all others are linearly interpolated.

Figure 3. Effect of the choice of air quality model, choice of exposure–response function, and racial/ethnic stratification of baseline mortality rates on nationwide PM_{2.5}-related avoided premature deaths by year and scenario. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals that reflect uncertainty in the hazard ratio functions from Turner et al. (73), Burnett et al. (44), Pope et al. (74), and Lepeule et al. (75).

Figure 4. Contribution of population growth, population aging, mortality rate changes, and $PM_{2.5}$ exposure changes to changes in future-year attributable $PM_{2.5}$ -related mortality totals relative to 2022 by year and scenario. Values shown here use model-averaged concentration data and the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (44).

Figure 5. Age-adjusted PM_{2.5}-attributable mortality rates by race/ethnicity, year, and scenario. Dotted lines in bar charts show values for the overall population. Values shown here use model-averaged concentration data and the exposure–response function from Burnett et al. (44).